

EFFECT OF ARTIFICIAL AGEING ON ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY (DSM-1) OF SOYBEAN

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted at the Experimental Farm, Department of Agricultural Botany, VNMKV, Parbhani, the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, VNMKV, Parbhani, the Quality Control Laboratory, MSSC Ltd., Parbhani and the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Golegaon, Hingoli, using soybean varieties MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335, and MAUS-162.

The study on the effects of ageing revealed that the seeds of all varieties (MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335, and MAUS-162) were artificially aged for various durations (24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 hours) at different temperatures (41°C, 42°C, 43°C, 44°C, and 45°C). Among the varieties, MAUS-162 was found to perform better in terms of moisture percentage, germination rate, germination index, seedling length, seed vigor index, and electrical conductivity, as compared to MAUS-71, MAUS-158, and JS-335 at the end of 120 hours of artificial ageing and 240 days of storage.

Additionally, the soybean variety MAUS-162 was superior in terms of biochemical parameters, such as malondialdehyde content, superoxide dismutase activity, peroxide activity, protein content, oil content, and dehydrogenase activity.

Keywords: soybean, ageing, temperature

Introduction

Soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill] is an important oil crop in the family Leguminosae, subfamily Papilionaceae, and genus *Glycine* L. Soybean is of particular importance in times of energy crisis and closure and plays central role in agriculture, and export. It has now become an oil and seed crop and is the cheapest alternative source of high-quality protein and cooking oil. Soybeans are high in protein and a rich source of carbohydrates and fats. They are a good source of vitamins, minerals and beneficial plant compounds, such as isoflavones. Soybeans have great potential as a particularly nutritious and protein-rich food. In general, stronger seeds can withstand high temperatures and high humidity while producing normal seedlings. Field appearance and seed storage capacity are closely related to seed vigor, which in turn, is negatively affected by different aging periods and storage conditions. The quality of soybean seeds is easily degraded, making it difficult to preserve for a long time. The physiological properties and storage capacity of seeds are influenced by humidity, which in-turn is controlled by the relative humidity of the surrounding air. Seeds are hygroscopic, they tend to absorb or lose moisture causing various biochemical changes in soybeans.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was carried out aiming at assessment of seed viability of plant species with high oil content and germination after seed had been stored and aged for certain period. Based on the aged seed vigour assessment, we can establish its field emergence capacity and possibility of forming vigorous and healthy plants which will be high yielding. The experimental material for the present investigation consists of four soybeans (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill.) varieties representing two maturity groups viz., MAUS-71 and MAUS-158 (Early maturity group: 93-95 days) and JS-335 and MAUS-162 (Late maturity group: 95-103 days). The seed material was evaluated for different seed quality parameters under natural and accelerated ageing conditions. Seed quality parameters were judged at 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 days of storage.

Results and Discussion

The data on the effect of varieties, temperature, and storage hours on the electrical conductivity of soybean seeds during artificial ageing are presented in Table 1 and graphically depicted in Figure 1.

The data revealed that the mean electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) was significantly influenced during all storage periods for the soybean varieties. Electrical conductivity increased with the progression of the storage period, regardless of variety, temperature, or storage hours. Electrical conductivity (EC) appears to be a key factor in determining seed storage viability from a retailer's perspective and can be used as a routine test for checking seed viability. A higher EC value corresponds to lower viability and vigor.

Significant differences in electrical conductivity among soybean varieties were observed throughout all storage periods, irrespective of variety, temperature, or storage hours. The mean electrical conductivity of the varieties MAUS-162, MAUS-158, MAUS-71, and JS-335 was 0.40, 0.41, 0.41, and 0.43 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, respectively, at the initial stage of soybean seed storage.

The highest electrical conductivity values were observed in soybean seeds stored at 45°C for 120 hours, with JS-335 recording 1.59 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, followed by MAUS-71 (1.57 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), MAUS-158 (1.57 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and MAUS-162 (1.55 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$).

The soybean variety MAUS-162 recorded lower electrical conductivity (0.63 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) compared to MAUS-158 (0.64 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), MAUS-71 (0.65 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and JS-335 (0.67 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) after 72 hours of accelerated ageing at 43°C. This marked the transition point for soybean storage, where MAUS-162 exhibited the lowest EC value. The electrical conductivity increased significantly with the continued extension of the storage period. It was observed that as the accelerated ageing time increased beyond 48 hours, the EC of the seed leachate also increased. This may be attributed to the loss of membrane integrity during ageing, which results in the leakage of electrolytes into the imbibition medium. An inverse correlation was noted between viability, vigor, germination, and the germination index with conductivity values (Dahiya et al., 2005).

Similar results have been reported in field beans (Narayanaswamy and Reddy, 1996), bitter melon (Shantappa et al., 2006), and rice (Singh and Kanujia, 2006). Panobianco and Vieira (1996) reported that different genotypes could be significantly affected by electrical conductivity, which increased with longer storage times. Shah and Wahida Sultan (2008) also showed that the conductivity of seed leachate increased with seed age in soybean varieties, similar to the findings of Agrawal and Siddiqui (1973). Kar Ling (1978) reported that the increase in electrical conductivity could be due to increased membrane permeability, which damages the grain during storage. Panobianco and Vieira (1996) also found that electrical conductivity varied among soybean varieties, likely due to differences in the lignin content of the seed coat. Higher lignin content is considered a desirable trait for improving soybean seed quality.

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Table 1: Effect of artificial ageing on Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) of soybean varieties

V X T X H Mean Table

	V1=MAUS-71					V2=MAUS-158					V3=JS-335					V4=MAUS-162				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
H 1	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5
	1	4	3	4	5	1	3	3	3	4	4	4	5	4	4	0	3	2	2	3
H 2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.7
	4	3	4	0	5	3	2	3	9	3	5	6	6	1	7	3	1	2	8	3
H 3	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.9	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.9
	5	6	5	7	7	5	5	4	6	6	7	9	7	7	0	3	3	3	4	4
H 4	0.7	0.8	0.7	1.1	1.3	0.7	0.8	0.7	1.1	1.3	0.7	0.8	0.7	1.1	1.3	0.7	0.7	0.7	1.1	1.3
	8	0	5	3	2	8	0	4	2	1	9	2	7	3	3	6	8	2	1	3
H 5	1.0	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.0	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.5	1.0	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.0	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.5
	7	1	3	3	7	6	1	2	9	7	8	1	3	3	9	4	0	1	2	5

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162

T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C

H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

VxT

	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	0.69	0.73	0.72	0.85	1.01	0.80
V2=MAUS-158	0.69	0.72	0.71	0.84	1.00	0.79
V3=JS-335	0.71	0.74	0.74	0.86	1.03	0.81
V4=MAUS-162	0.67	0.71	0.70	0.82	0.94	0.77
Mean T	0.69	0.73	0.72	0.84	0.99	

VxH

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	0.45	0.59	0.72	0.96	1.28	0.80
V2=MAUS-158	0.45	0.58	0.71	0.95	1.27	0.79
V3=JS-335	0.46	0.61	0.74	0.97	1.29	0.81
V4=MAUS-162	0.44	0.57	0.64	0.94	1.24	0.77
Mean H	0.45	0.59	0.70	0.95	1.27	

TxH

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean T
T1	0.42	0.54	0.65	0.78	1.06	0.69
T2	0.44	0.53	0.66	0.80	1.21	0.73
T3	0.43	0.54	0.65	0.75	1.22	0.72
T4	0.43	0.60	0.76	1.12	1.29	0.84
T5	0.54	0.75	0.79	1.32	1.57	0.99
Mean H	0.45	0.59	0.70	0.95	1.27	

Note: V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162

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TABLE OF SEM, SED AND C.D.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(V)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Factor(T)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Interaction V X T	0.01	0.00	0.00
Factor(H)	0.00	0.00	0.00
Interaction V X H	0.01	0.00	0.00
Interaction T X H	0.01	0.00	0.00
Interaction V X T X H	0.01	0.01	0.00

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162

T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C

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Fig. 1: Effect of artificial ageing on Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) of soybean varieties

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